

5-SHO‘BA

TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH

A METHOD FOR MEASURING THE PIEZOELECTRIC EFFECT ON A MICHELSON INTERFEROMETER

PhD. Docent. A.I.Mamadjanov,

Namangan engineering-construction institute, Uzbekistan,

mamadjanov3084@gmail.com

A.Rahimov, H.Xasanov

Namangan engineering-construction institute, Uzbekistan,

Annotation. This article describes the method of measuring the piezoelectric effect using the Michelson interferometer, and it is shown that its measurement accuracy is in the order of 10^{-7} m.

Key words: piezoelectric, crystal, interferometer, wave, laser, path difference.

In 1880, the brothers Jacques and Pierre Curie discovered that when certain natural crystals were compressed or stretched, electric charges appeared on the crystal faces. The brothers called this phenomenon “piezoelectricity” (the Greek word “piezo” means “press”), and they themselves called such crystals piezoelectric crystals. As it turned out, tourmaline, quartz and other natural crystals, as well as many artificially grown crystals, have a piezoelectric effect. Such crystals regularly add to the list of already known piezoelectric crystals [1]. When such a piezoelectric crystal is stretched or compressed in the desired direction, opposite electric charges arise on some of its faces, which have a small potential difference.

If, however, interconnected electrodes are placed on these faces, then at the moment of compression or stretching of the crystal, a short electrical impulse will appear in the circuit formed by the electrodes. This will be a manifestation of the piezoelectric effect. At constant pressure, such an impulse will not occur. The inherent properties of these crystals make it possible to manufacture precise and sensitive instruments [2].

The piezoelectric crystal has high elasticity. When the deforming force is

removed, the crystal, without inertia, returns to its original volume and shape. It is worth making an effort again or changing the one already applied, and it will immediately respond with a new current pulse [3]. It is the best recorder of very weak mechanical vibrations reaching it. The current strength in the circuit of an oscillating crystal is small, and this was a stumbling block at the time of the discovery of the piezoelectric effect by the Curie brothers.

In modern technology, this is not an obstacle, because the current can be amplified millions of times. Now some crystals are known that have a very significant piezoelectric effect. And the current received from them can be transmitted over wires over long distances even without prior amplification [4].

Piezoelectric crystals have found application in ultrasonic flaw detection, to detect defects inside metal products. In electromechanical converters for radio frequency stabilization, in multi-channel telephone communication filters, when several conversations are carried out simultaneously on one wire, in pressure and gain sensors, in adapters, in ultrasonic soldering - in many technical fields, piezoelectric crystals have taken their unshakable position.

An important property of piezoelectric crystals turned out to be the inverse piezoelectric effect. If charges of opposite signs are applied to certain faces of a crystal, then the crystals themselves will be deformed. If you impose electrical vibrations of sound frequency on a crystal, it will begin to oscillate with the same frequency, and sound waves will be excited in the surrounding air. So the same crystal can act both as a microphone and as a speaker.

Another feature of piezoelectric crystals has made them an integral part of modern radio engineering. Possessing its own frequency of mechanical oscillations, the crystal begins to oscillate especially strongly at the moment when the frequency of the supplied alternating voltage coincides with it.

This is a manifestation of electromechanical resonance, on the basis of which piezoelectric stabilizers are created, thanks to which the frequency is maintained constant in the generators of continuous oscillations.

In a similar way, they also react to mechanical vibrations, the frequency of which coincides with the frequency of natural oscillations of the piezocrystal. This allows you to create acoustic devices that distinguish from all the sounds reaching them only those that are needed for certain purposes.

For piezo devices do not take whole crystals. Crystals are sawn into layers strictly oriented relative to their crystallographic axes, these layers are then used

to make rectangular or round plates, which are then ground to a certain size. The thickness of the plates is carefully maintained, since the resonant frequency of oscillations depends on it. One or more plates connected to metal layers on two wide surfaces are called piezoelectric elements.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the Michelson interferometer. When the condenser C is energized, electric field changes and length of cristall to Δl due to piezoelectric effect. As a result, it is possible to observe the interference pattern shift on the SC screen. This can be explained by the following equations. Assuming that the known intervals l_1 and l_2 correspond to the maximum interference

$$l_1 = \pm m_1 \lambda_0, \quad l_2 = \pm m_2 \lambda_0 \quad (1)$$

Changes in optical path differences is

$$\Delta = l_2 - l_1 = \pm \Delta m \lambda_0 \quad (2)$$

Here Δ is the change in the linear dimensions of an object in a electric field. This change can be compared to the change in the path difference of light on the Michelson interferometer. From the above equation, it can be said that as the body changes at each wavelength, one interference pattern shifts into one order. This means that linear changes in an object can be detected graphically by shifting the interference pattern.

Conclusion

This paper discusses the possibilities of measuring the piezoelectric effect using a Michelson interferometer. It has been shown that with changes in the external electric field, it is possible to measure changes in the linear dimensions 10^{-7} of some crystals standing in the same field. The study of such materials could make a significant contribution to the further development of nanotechnology in the future.

References

1. M. A. Khashan, “Comparison of group and phase velocities of light using the Michelson interferometer,” *Optik* 64, 285–297.(1983).
2. S. Diddams and J. C. Diels, “Dispersion measurements with white-light interferometry,” *J. Opt. Soc. Am. B* 13, 1120–1129.(1996).
3. Z. Bor, K. Osvay, B. Racz, and G. Szabo, “Group refractive index measurement by Michelson interferometer,” *Opt. Commun.* 78, 109–112. (1990).
4. M. Beck and I. A. Walmsley, “Measurement of group delay with high temporal and spectral resolution,” *Opt. Lett.* 15, 492–494 .(1990).